

Influence of Cost Control Practices on Performance of Fish Farming Projects Funded by the Kiambu County Government, KENYA

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Abstract: *The fish farming Projects in Kiambu County has not performed as per the intended plans for food security, improving nutrition status, creating employment and eradication of poverty among the beneficiaries. Cost of inputs, technology and marketing challenges of individual farmers has rendered sustainability of profitability of farm pond projects uncertain. Despite the high number of fisheries projects born annually in the county, their mortality rate remains very high even though limited scholars are trying to research on the causative factors. The main objective of continuous improvement programs is not only to meet customer's requirements, but to do it at the lowest cost as well, this study focused on the cost control area in project management. The general objective of this research was to determine the influence of cost control practices on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the Kiambu County government. Specifically, the study sought to determine the influence of budgeting, standard costing and financial training on performance of fish farming projects. The study was anchored on the performance theory, theory of budget and the theory of cost. The study was conducted using descriptive research design in order to draw an accurate snapshot of some aspects of cost control practices in fish farming projects. The target populations comprised 60 fish farming projects. Due to the manageable size of population, census approach was appropriate for the study. Structured questionnaires were used as the instrument for data collection. A pilot study was done in Nakuru County using six projects. Validity test of the research instrument was determined through consultation with university research supervisor and practitioners. The data was analyzed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Correlation analysis was used to estimate the strength and direction of the relationship between variables and regression model was used to make predictions about the population and analysis of the sample. The results were presented in tables. The study established that standard costing ($r = 0.644^{**}$, $p = .000$) and financial training ($r = 0.637^{**}$, $p = .000$) had a strong positive correlation with performance of fish projects while budgeting ($r = 0.135$, $p = .355$) had a weak positive correlation with performance of fish projects which indicates that the level of standard costing and financial training significantly influences the performance of fish farming projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. The fitted model R-square of 0.512 was an indication that the three cost control practices explained 51.2% of the variation in the performance of fish projects. The study concluded that standard costing and financial training was significant predictors of performance of fish farming projects while budgeting though a predictor was not significant at 5%. The study recommended that government agencies should enhance financial training amongst project participants in order to enhance their outputs. Further, standard costing should be structured into the project mechanism for enhanced performance. Since past studies report the importance of budgeting in the project process, mechanism of simplifying the budget process should be inculcated in the financial training programs.*

Key Terms: *budgeting, standard costing, financial training, performance, and fish farming projects.*

I. Background to the Study

A project is a temporary venture that is undertaken to produce a unique product, service or result (project management institute guide 2008). It is typically meant to do something that is new and has never been done before. All the projects that are planned need to be guided properly, in order to receive the expected output, and can achieve the goals at the end of the project. In project management there are triple constraints that must be faced by the project manager. The three constraints in project management are scope, cost, and time goal. The control of various costs is a very important task for any project where the project manager needs to oversee.

The project deliverables should address the problem or a need that had been analyzed before the initiation of the project, (PMBOK guide 2008). According to PMI (2013), aligning projects with the organizations strategic objectives brings value to an organization. Implementing successful projects generates positive effects on the organization, influencing not just short and medium, but also long term developments. Cost is with no doubt the most important concern in any development venture, and more so in both public and private projects. Memon *et al.*, (2010) recounts that poor cost performance in public projects is a major concern for both contractors and clients. In order to control costs, it is important to exercise foresight of the various project related determinants and address the magnitude of their effects. Elhag *et al.*, (2005) agreed that realizing and understanding cost determinants will enhance the cost estimator's competence, hence sufficiently delivering a more sustainable and reliable cost modeling and estimating technique.

Cost control is the practice of identifying and reducing business expenses to increase profits, and it begins with the process of developing a budget. A project owner compares actual results with the budgeted expectations and if actual costs are higher than planned, the manager has to take action to reverse the possibility of losses (Njagi *et al.* 2013). Cost control in aquaculture business means a search for better and more economical ways of operating fish farming projects. Cost control is simply the prevention of waste within the existing environment. The poor cost control performance of many projects is a common problem worldwide resulting in a significant amount of cost overruns (Aris *et al.*, 2013). The problem with cost control is not actually the techniques that are used, but rather the poor management of those techniques and the laxity in supervision (ICTAD/CM/2008). The best way to understand why it is so important to manage costs when undertaking a project is to actually conceptualize it with the help of a simple thought experiment like how project will work out when you implement project cost management as opposed to when you do not implement project cost management (Mutya, 2018).

Small projects survive on a day-to-day basis for most farms and manufacturing businesses. Though large projects tend to receive the most attention, small projects are just as important and help keep a business running. Cost control on small projects is so important because losing small portion of money on a small project progressively will result to these small amounts adding up over time resulting to huge losses and project closure in the long run. Following a set of small project cost control best practices is therefore very critical (Crowder, 2018). In the building projects in Syria, cost control practices are low since 62.86% of the projects lack work break down structure (WBS) while determining the project budget, 62.86% of the projects do not use specialized programs to estimate and control costs, 55.71% do not apply change control and do not have reports of actual performance. This led to increased organizational expenditure and lowered the performance levels, thus the need for proper cost control systems to minimize costs and promote performance (Thompson, 2019).

Similarly, Innoson Nigeria Company limited Enugu, reported that cost of products manufactured has been very expensive beyond the reach of common Nigerians. Prices of goods and services are gradually increasing day by day, and due to the fact that the sole aim of the producer is to make profit they end up making use of low quality materials for production so as to reduce cost of production and maximize profit. However, with the increase of competitors around, most of the producers have thought it wise to manufacture or package a quality product and also enhance their profit level. Therefore for better performance, there is need to maintain quality and device proper cost control measures to minimize costs and improve on project performance. Osisioma (2010) observed that manufacturing firms, particularly automobile industries witnessed a drop in sales level, an accumulation of unsold stocks, and a declining demand level leading to a fall in profit level that was caused by failure to observe cost control practices in the manufacturing process.

Managing cost of production is therefore the focal point of any project manager, as increased competition in the modern business environment among companies; coupled with a turbulent market system, allowing for free entry and exit of market participants. With the growing presence of vocal customers demanding high quality products at lower prices companies are necessitated to upgrade or modify their processes constantly in order to lower cost of products or services they trade (Jayeola, Sokefun, & Oginni, 2012). In order to stay ahead of market competition and meet the growing

customer demands for fish and fish products, farmers must redesign measures aimed at reduction of production cost which affect the market prices of their products (Sani & Allahverdzadeh, 2012).

A study conducted by Chidi & Shadare (2011) in Nigeria focusing on challenges confronting cost control in firms in Nigeria found that budgeting among firms faced challenges by the businesses not taking ownership or not being accountable, there being lack of cooperation and participation and a lack of understanding of the budgeting process.

Kieu (2014) found out that efficiency in accounting information system and financial reporting and analysis enhanced profitability. Use of complex investment appraisal techniques such as net present value (NPV) and internal rate of return (IRR) methods have a positive impact on the profitability of business projects. Kumar & Shafabi, (2011) found positive relationship in that cost control techniques such as standard costing, sourcing and budget system limit the high cost that could be incurred and as a result for the same level of income, the expenses were lower which results to increase in profitability.

In his study on cost benefit analysis on the fish farming projects, Wambua (2015) analyzed the effect change in the cost of inputs on the net present value (NPV). The values of the respective attributes were varied in all the cases by either decreasing them up to -20% of their presumed value or increasing them by 20% of their value. The net change in the value of the NPV was observed, results summary revealed that NPV is by far most sensitive to the market price of fish, followed by the cost of feeds and the average pond production.

Kenya's aquaculture sector plays an important role in the country's economic and social development, and includes the aquaculture (farmed fish) and the capture fisheries. The fisheries sub-sector earns the country an average of USD 70 million (KES 5.3 billion) annually from exports. Besides generating foreign revenue, aquaculture provides a source of subsistence and livelihood to the rural poor. Estimates from the State Department of Fisheries indicate that fish production significantly increased from 1,035MT (2004) to 23,501MT (2013) driven by increased resource allocation to the sector through the Economic Stimulus Program (ESP) initiated by the Government of Kenya (GOK) in 2007 (MALF, 2013).

The Kiambu County is located in the Central highlands of Kenya in the former Central Province, close to Kenya's capital, Nairobi Covering an area of 2,543.42 square kilometers and density of 660.2/km². It has a total population of 1,623, 282, it's also considered one of the wealthiest counties in Kenya with urbanization of up to 62.3% of the land owing to Nairobi city growth in the north. It is a leading innovative commercial hub that shares its borders with five other counties; Nakuru and Kajiado to the West, Murang'a and Nyandarua to the North and Nairobi to the South. The County relies mostly on agriculture and industries to sustain its economy.

The growth of fish farming in Kiambu County has necessitated a high demand of quality fish seed for the commonly cultured species; African catfish and Nile tilapia. (Kenya's Aquaculture Brief 2017). In their research on fish farming in Kiambu County, Nicholas et al, (2015) observed that the employment status of fish farmers in Kiambu County showed that majority of the respondents 79.3% were self-employed in agriculture sector. That means their financial stability is uncertain given the rapid fluctuations of rains and agriculture products' prices. Specific financing challenges faced by fish farmers across the county vary at different stages of growth. Mutunga (2015) studied the influence of financial stability on fish farming projects in Machakos. The study showed that financial stability had significant relationship with performance of fish farming projects in Machakos County.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is evident that project performance is still a major challenge in many developing countries as many of projects implemented at huge costs often tend to experience difficulties with sustainability. Cost control is of utmost importance in every project concern, the negligence of which will affect the earnings at any point in time. In controlling costs, wastage is eliminated during the course of production and even during the administrative, selling and distribution of the product. The fish farming Projects in Kiambu County has not performed as per the intended plans of food security, improving nutrition status, creating employment and eradicating poverty among the beneficiaries. Kenya farm fisheries declined from 15000mt in 2016 to 12,400mt in 2017. Statistics in Kiambu County fisheries office indicated 1532 fish ponds in 2018 compared to 3813 in 2013 (State of aquaculture in Kenya 2018). This accounts to about 59.82 % reduction which may be stalling or are completely abandoned. High cost of inputs, technology and marketing challenges of individual farmers rendered sustainability of profitable on farm pond projects uncertain. Despite the high number of fisheries projects born annually in the county, their mortality rate remains very high even with scholars trying to research on the causative factors. The failure to meet the objectives of the economic stimulus program (ESP) fisheries projects has necessitated the Kiambu county government through the fisheries extension officers to organize farmer groups and of

farm income generating groups related to the sub sector which were funded with startup capital for inputs in 2017/2018 year. The vision of the county fisheries department is to develop a public-private partnership in order to form a robust aquaculture industry in the county. This type of partnership must combine approaches such as cost control practices, financial planning, management of human capital of individuals and groups engaging in fish farming to meet its objectives. The fish farming projects initiated through the county government and managed through farmer groups and learning institutions were provided with equal inputs in terms of construction cost, seeds and feeds. Despite the equal share of investment capital, some projects performance is quite vibrant and profitable while others are still struggling to survive under group management. This issue poses a major challenge towards realizing the fisheries department vision of public-private partnership in aquaculture development. It's upon this background that this study sought to determine the influence of cost control practices on the performance of fish farming projects that were initiated through the county government of Kiambu.

1.3 General Objective

The general objective of the study was to determine the influence of cost control practices on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the in Kiambu County government.

1.4 Specific Objectives:

- i. To determine the influence of budgeting on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the in Kiambu County government.
- ii. To examine the influence of standard costing on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the in Kiambu County government.
- iii. To assess the influence of financial training on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the in Kiambu County government.

1.5 Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: Budgeting has no significant effect on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the in Kiambu County government.

H₀₂: Standard costing has no significant influence on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the in Kiambu County government.

H₀₃: Financial training has no significant effect on the performance of fish farming projects funded by the in Kiambu County government.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study will help identify the cost control practices that have a significant influence on the performance of fisheries projects. The findings will be significant to the fisheries project managers and individual farmers since they will get to acquire knowledge of the cost control practices needed to improve on the profitability and hence high return on investment of the projects. The Government will use it to formulate policies and frameworks that encourage farmers' trainings on the project cost control practices in agribusiness enterprises. It will also caution the farmers and project managers against financial crisis arising from poor cost control practices. The study findings may also be adopted by other agribusiness sub-sectors such as crops and livestock production enterprise. The new entrants will be enlightened on, fish farming investment opportunities, constrains and capital requirements for better fisheries project performance, growth and sustainability. The study will provide a reference material for future researchers and scholars who would want to further venture into this area of study.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study was carried out in the 12 sub counties of Kiambu County. The study focused on the influence of cost control practices on the performance of 60 fisheries projects initiated and funded by the Kiambu county government in 2017/2018 financial year.

II. Theoretical Review

The study reviewed theories that were used to test hypothesis: the theory of cost, theory of budget and the theory of the performance

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework describes the relationship between the main concepts of a study. The framework presented the relationship between project performance as the dependent variable to budgeting, financial training, and cost forecasting as the independent variables.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

III. Research Design

Research design refers to the methodological guidelines put in place for collecting and analyzing data (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). The study adopted a descriptive survey design to identify the relationship between the study variables. It focused on project managers for fisheries demonstration projects as the unit of analysis (Kothari, 2014). Descriptive research is designed to provide a picture of a situation as it naturally happens. This design is more formalized and typically structured with clearly stated investigative questions. The design was used to obtain information that describes the phenomena by asking individuals about their perceptions, attitudes, behaviors and values (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). The study employed quantitative approaches to gather information on the influence of cost control practices on the performance of fish farming projects funded by Kiambu County.

3.2 Target Population

Study population according to Mugenda & Mugenda, (2003) is the entire group of individuals, events or subjects possessing common observable characteristics of interest to the researcher. The target population was 60 fish farming projects funded by Kiambu County government in the financial year 2017/2018.

3.5.1 Sample Size

The target population for this study was small and therefore a census technique was used. The sample size comprised of 60 projects.

3.6 Data Collection Instruments

Primary Data was collected by use of structured questionnaires. The structured questions were constructed in Likert scale and assigned numerical values to make quantitative analysis possible (Khan *et al.*, 2011). This provided uniform responses and allowed ease in analysis of quantitative data. The structured questionnaires will be in five parts. Section A contained questions on the background of the respondents and was to obtain data on gender, age, and work experience of respondents. Section B was to collect data on the influence of budgeting practices on project performance. Section C will collect data to determine the influence of standard costing on performance of fish farming projects. Section D was to collect data on the influence of financial training on the performance of fish farming projects. Section E was to collect data to assess the general performance of the fish farming projects funded by the Kiambu county government using various performance indicators. The Questionnaire was preferred due to its suitability and ease of administration and also allowed the researcher to reach entire sample within limited time..

3.7 Validity

Validity is the degree to which results obtained from the analysis of the data actually represents the phenomenon under study. Kothari (2004) pointed out that validity measures the accuracy of the instruments in obtaining the anticipated data which can meet the objectives of the study. Validity determines whether the research tool truly measures that which it is intended to measure or how truthful the research results are.

3.8 Reliability

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), reliability is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results or data after repeated trials. After establishing the validity the researcher tested the reliability of the instrument. A pre-test was conducted in one other area with similar characteristics to the study sample. Internal consistency which is the ability of the items in a group to measure the same attributes was tested using the Crombach’s Alpha test (Shende *et al.*, 2012). Crombach’s Alpha of 0.7 and above was used to confirm the reliability of the instrument. The results obtained from the pilot study assisted the researcher in revising the questionnaire to make sure that it covered the objectives of the study. Care was taken to ensure that the tested subjects did not form part of the study sample so as not to compromise the quality of responses. The findings of the reliability test were as shown in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Reliability Test

Study Variables	Number of Tests	Alpha Values
Budgeting	5	0.769
Standard Costing	5	0.778
Financial Training	5	0.737
Performance of Fish Projects	6	0.729

The reliability test shown in Table 3.2 produced alpha (α) values of greater than 0.70 and thus the data collection tool was deemed reliable.

IV. Data Analysis and Presentation

4.1 Descriptive Analysis Results

The researcher sought to establish the influence of cost control practices on performance of fish projects funded by Kiambu County. The selected practices were budgeting, standard costing and financial training. The dependent variable for was performance of projects.

4.4.1 Budgeting

Budget provides standard cost for purposes of cost control and is one of the ways of controlling cost in organizations. The findings on budgeting are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4. 1: Budgeting

Statement	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
The farmers usually do budget estimates before engaging themselves in fish farming projects investments.	0	6.1	4.1	55.1	34.7	4.18	.782
Farmers analyze all the variable costs such as labor cost, feeds, fingerlings and include it in their fish project’s budget for a given production period	0	2	14.3	46.9	36.7	4.18	.755
Farmers often understand the fixed costs rent and member subscriptions associated with the fish farming projects and include them in their production period budget	0	2	6.1	55.1	36.7	4.27	.670
The farmers usually make production projections and hence include sales projections of their harvest in the budget for each production period	2	2	8.2	49	38.8	4.20	.841
Farmers incur additional costs during the production period outside what is budgeted for.	0	0	10.2	55.1	34.7	4.24	.630

As seen in Table 4.1, the results were within one standard deviation. Farmers usually do budget estimates before engaging themselves in fish farming projects investments (M = 4.18, SD = 0.782). The study also established that farmers analyze all the variable costs such as labor cost, feeds, fingerlings and include it in their fish project’s budget for a given production period (M = 4.18, SD = 0.755). Similarly, it was found that farmers understood fixed costs such as rent and member subscriptions associated with the fish farming projects and include them in their production period budget (M = 4.27, SD = 0.670). Furthermore, it was found that farmers usually made production projections and hence include sales projections of their harvest in the budget for each production period (M = 4.20, SD = 0.841). Finally, it was established that farmers incur additional costs during the production period outside what is budgeted for (M = 4.24, SD = 0.630). The findings agree with those of Eton *et al.*, (2018), saw that cash budget has a strong relationship with organization performance. They also indicated that cash budget stabilizes organizational profit levels and ensures that organization expenditures are in line with planned cash flows and enhances the organizations capacity to predict excess expenditures.

4.4.2 Standard Costing

Standard costing can be seen as the expected cost per unit of the products during a production period and it aims at measuring performance, control the deviations, and deciding the price of the product when preparing for the market. Table 4.2 presents findings on standard costing.

Table 4. 2: Standard Costing

Statement	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
Farmers usually make production cost estimates in relation to the previous production period.	0	2	12.2	46.9	38.8	4.22	.743
Farmers calculate the actual production cost at the end of the production period and make comparison with the estimates made during the start of the production cycle.	0	2	12.2	61.2	24.5	4.08	.672
Farmers calculate the cost variance to determine if there is any loss incurred during the production period.	0	14.3	26.5	36.7	22.4	3.67	.987
Farmers determine the harvest volume at end of production cycle to establish any variance with the amount stocked at the start of the production cycle	0	8.2	18.4	38.8	34.7	4.00	.935
The total cost of production in fisheries projects largely determines the pricing of fish during marketing.	6.1	12.2	26.5	28.6	26.5	3.57	1.190

From the findings, it was established that farmers usually make production cost estimates in relation to the previous production period (M = 4.22, SD = 0.743). further, the study found that farmers calculate the actual production cost at the end of the production period and make comparison with the estimates made during the start of the production cycle (M = 4.08, SD = 0.672). Similarly, it was established that farmers calculate the cost variance to determine if there is any loss incurred during the production period (M =3.67, SD = 0.987). The study also found that farmers determine the harvest volume at end of production cycle to establish any variance with the amount stocked at the start of the production cycle (M = 4.00, SD = 0.935). Finally, the study established that the total cost of production in fisheries projects largely determines the pricing of fish during marketing (M = 3.57, SD = 1.190). The findings concur with findings by Eyisi (2017) who noted that standard costing acts as a yardstick against actual as compared with budgeted costs. This means that standard costing provides basis whereby performance may be measured based on what product to produce, how much quantity to use and the expected levels of activity which are compared with the actual results obtained.

4.4.3 Financial Training

Financial training helps farmers to recognize the importance of regular saving and thoughtful expenditure. The findings on financial training are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Financial Training

Statement	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
Farmers analyze their capital position before engaging in fish farming projects	0	6.1	22.4	49	22.4	3.88	.832
Farmers do profit analysis of fish farming before undertaking the projects.	2	6.1	24.5	34.7	32.7	3.90	1.005
Farmers save part of their profit from fish farming which they can use in the following production cycle or other farm investments.	0	0	16.3	42.9	40.8	4.24	.723
Farmers keep regular track records for all activities during the production period.	2	2	22.4	46.9	26.5	3.94	.876
Farmers normally develop market plans with their customers to minimize post-harvest spoilage by making arrangements with buyer or by contract engagements	2	12.2	26.5	38.8	20.4	3.63	1.014

From the findings in Table 4.3, it was established that farmers analyze their capital position before engaging in fish farming projects (M =3.88, SD = 0.832). Similarly, farmers do profit analysis of fish farming before undertaking the projects (M = 3.90, SD = 1.005). It was also established that farmers save part of their profit from fish farming which they use in the following production cycle or other farm investments (M = 4.24, SD = 0.723). The study also found that farmers keep regular track records for all activities during the production period. (M = 3.94, SD = 0.876). Finally, the study established that farmers normally develop market plans with their customers to minimize post-harvest spoilage by making arrangements with buyer or by contract engagements (M = 3.63, SD = 1.014). The findings tally with those of Mahdzan & Tahiani (2013) who explored the impact of financial training on individual saving in Malaysia and found that financial training, both basic and advanced knowledge are related with high saving.

4.4.4 Performance of Fish Projects

Project performance is one of the most important objectives of cost control practices because one goal of project management is to maximize the owner's wealth. Thus, performance is very important in determining the success or failure of a project. The findings on performance of fish projects are shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Performance of Fish Projects

Statement	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
Fish farming project income is able to pay all short and long term obligations.	2	0	10.2	53.1	34.7	4.18	.782
Fish farming investment has realized high returns over the past two years.	2	2	16.3	61.2	18.4	3.92	.786
Fish farming projects have met stakeholder objectives of food security, nutrition and poverty eradication.	0	8.2	28.6	42.9	20.4	3.76	.879
Market of farmed fish has met consumer needs in terms of quality and quantity.	2	8.2	22.4	44.9	22.4	3.78	.963
Farmed fish has gained strong market position over the last two years.	2	4.1	20.4	38.8	34.7	4.00	.957
There is assured fish farming projects sustainability in the county.	0	8.2	18.4	44.9	28.6	3.94	.899

As seen in Table 4.4, it was established that fish farming project income was able to pay all short and long term obligations ($M = 4.18$, $SD = 0.782$). Furthermore, the study established that fish farming investment had realized high returns over the past two years ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.786$). Similarly, fish farming projects had met stakeholder objectives of food security, nutrition and poverty eradication ($M = 3.76$, $SD = 0.879$). The study also established that the market of farmed fish had met consumer needs in terms of quality and quantity ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.963$). Similarly, the study established that farmed fish had gained strong market position over the last two years ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.957$). Finally, the study established that there was assured fish farming projects sustainability in the county. ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.899$). As noted by Eniola *et al.*, (2015), project performance is one of the most important objectives of cost control practices because one goal of project management is to maximize the owner's wealth. Thus, performance is very important in determining the success or failure of fish farming projects.

4.5 Diagnostic Tests

For regression analysis to be undertaken, since it is a parametric estimation technique, a number of assumptions must be met for the resulting parameter estimates to be unbiased and efficient. Four assumptions namely; linearity of variables, multicollinearity, homoscedasticity and normality of residuals were tested and their results are discussed in the following subsections.

4.5.1 Linearity of Variables

The assumption of linearity in parametric estimations requires that there should be a linear relationship between the dependent and the independent variables under study. A linear relationship exists when a change in the dependent variable due to one unit change in the independent variable is constant, regardless of the value of the independent variable. The additive principle requires that the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable is truly independent of other variables in the model. A plot of standardized predicted values versus residuals indicating a horizontal scatter indicates a linear and additive relationship. As seen in Figure 4.1., the scatter plot does not indicate any curved distribution pattern, an indication that the relationship between the independent variables and performance of fish farming projects assumes a linear relationship.

Figure 4. 1: Linearity of Variables

4.5.2 Test of Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity is a phenomenon where one independent variable is linearly predicted by another independent variable with a substantial degree of accuracy. A commonly accepted test of multicollinearity is through Variance Inflation Factors (VIF). VIF factors of less than 5 are widely accepted as an indication of limited correlation between the independent variables and therefore pose insignificant influence on accuracy of parameter estimation.

Table 4. 5: Collinearity Statistics

	Tolerance	VIF
Budgeting	.995	1.005
Standard Costing	.606	1.650
Financial Training	.607	1.648

From Table 4.5, it was established that all the VIF of the three independent variables were found to be less than five, an indication that there was absence of multicollinearity.

4.5.3 Test of Homoscedasticity

Homoscedasticity is a phenomenon identified with the presence of constant variance in the error term, an assumption that is violated when outliers or extreme values are present in the data. The presence of heteroscedasticity leads to unrealistically wide standard errors leading to poor parameter estimates. To test this assumption, a residual versus predicted values plot is used. A funnel shape in the scatter plot is an indication of heteroscedastic data.

Figure 4. 2: Homoscedasticity Test

As seen in Figure 4.2., the scatter points of predicted versus residuals spreads evenly across the plot area, an indication of homoscedasticity.

4.5.4 Normality of Residuals

The presence of normally distributed residuals in a regression model not only enhance the quality of hypothesis test results but also greatly strengthen the validity of the t and F test statistic and the associated P-values. A plot of residuals with points that fall close to the diagonal reference line closely indicates non-violation of the normality assumption.

Figure 4. 3: Normality test

Figure 4.3.indicates a close mesh a strong indication of normality of residuals.

4.6 Correlation Analysis

Table 4. 6: Correlations

		Performance of Fish Projects
Budgeting	Pearson Correlation	.135
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.355
	N	49
Standard Costing	Pearson Correlation	.644**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	49
Financial Training	Pearson Correlation	.637**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	49

The findings of the correlation analysis on the influence of the independent variables on performance of fish projects are shown in Table 4.6. From the correlation analysis, standard costing ($r = 0.644^{**}$, $p = .000$) and financial training ($r = 0.637^{**}$, $p = .000$) had a strong positive correlation with performance of fish projects while budgeting ($r = 0.135$, $p = .355$) had a weak positive correlation with performance of fish projects. The correlation analysis therefore indicates that the level of standard costing and financial training significantly influences the performance of fish farming projects in Kiambu County, Kenya

However, budgeting is not a significant predictor of performance of fish projects though it positively influenced performance. However, the study findings on budgeting contrast those of Adebayo *et al.*, (2014) who found that budget is an effective tool for management in coordinating the affairs of the organization. The findings submit that to prepare a budget, an organization must know where it is heading to since budgets are futuristic in nature. A system of budgetary control compels a firm to look into the future and use all techniques that can be used to shape the future. Further, budgets enable comparison between budgeted figures and actual results on timely basis which enables management to know where deviations are occurring and to take corrective measures.

4.7 Regression Analysis

Multiple regression techniques provide estimates the relationship between a single dependent variable and several independent predictor variables (Creswell, 2012). The choice of a multiple regression model was based on the need to determine parameter estimates, obtain a fitted multiple regression model and to provide a basis for hypothesis testing. With all the regression assumptions examined and no violation found, the data was fitted with a multiple linear regression model and individual coefficients tested at 5% significance level. The results of the regression analysis were as summarized in Table 4.7, 4.8 and 4.9.

Table 4. 7: Regression Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.716 ^a	.512	.479	.42654

a. Predictors: (Constant), Budgeting, Standard Costing, Financial Training

b. Dependent Variable: Performance of Fish Projects

The fitted model R-square of 0.512 was an indication that the three cost control practices explained 51.2% of the variation in the dependent variable; performance of fish projects. Further, the adjusted r-squared value of 0.479 which takes care of the degrees of freedom of the model indicated 47.9% of the variation in the dependent variable was explained by the independent variables. As seen in the Table 4.10, the ANOVA findings indicated that the multiple regression model was statistically significant (F = 15.379, P < 0.05).

Table 4.8: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	8.591	3	2.864	15.379	.000 ^b
Residual	8.187	45	.182		
Total	16.778	48			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Fish Projects

With the model achieving statistical significance, the estimated coefficients of each cost control practice were as shown in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9: Multiple Regression Model Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.445	.912		.488	.628
Budgeting	.168	.199	.088	.847	.402
Standard Costing	.346	.116	.399	2.984	.005
Financial Training	.361	.127	.382	2.854	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Fish Projects

From Table 4.9, the unstandardized coefficients were used to develop the following model:

$$Y = 0.445 + 0.168X_1 + 0.346X_2 + 0.361X_3 + 0.42654$$

Where: Y= Performance of Fish Farming Projects, X₁= Budgeting, X₂= Standard Costing and X₃ = Financial Training
 From the model, holding all the independent variables constant, performance of fish projects would increase by a factor of 0.445. Further, a unit increase in budgeting would cause an increase of performance of fish projects by a factor of 0.168, a unit increase in standard costing would cause an increase of performance of fish projects by a factor of 0.346 and a unit increase in financial training would cause an increase of performance of fish projects by a factor of 0.361.

4.8 Hypothesis Testing

The study sought to establish the influence of cost control practices on performance of fish projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. In order to arrive at a definitive conclusion on the influence of each cost control practice on performance of fish projects, hypothesis testing was undertaken at 5% significance using p-values. In each case the null hypothesis is rejected if the p-value is less than 0.05 otherwise we fail to reject if it is more than 0.05. The first hypothesis stated as follows: **H₀₁**: Budgeting has no significant influence on performance of fish projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. As seen in Table 4.9, budgeting ($t = 0.847$, $P=0.402$), since the p-value obtained was greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis leading to a conclusion that budgeting has no significant influence on performance of fish projects. The findings are contrary with those found by Adebayo *et al.*, (2014) who found that budgeting is an effective tool for management in coordinating the affairs of the organization. Similarly, the findings contrast those of Eton *et al.*, (2018) who found that budgeting had a strong relationship with project performance.

The second hypothesis of the study stated: **H₀₂**: Standard costing has no significant influence on performance of fish projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. From Table 4.9, standard costing ($t = 2.984$, $P= 0.005$), since the p-value obtained was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected leading to a conclusion that standard costing significantly influences performance of fish projects. The findings agree with those of Lawal (2017) who opined that standard costing is one of the techniques which enhance the attainment of cost reduction as it predetermines the respective costs of material, labor and overhead before the commencement of the production process. Their study further noted that with this also comes the benefit of achieving the most with the least cost and reduction of wastages in the course of production. Similar findings were found by Eyisi (2017) who noted that the advantages of standard costing is that it acts as a yardstick against actual as compared with budgeted costs. This means that standard costing provides basis whereby performance may be measured based on what product to produce, how much quantity to use and the expected levels of activity in comparison with the actual results.

The last hypothesis stated as: **H₀₃**: Financial training has no significant influence on performance of fish projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. Based on the findings on Table 4.9, financial training ($t = 2.854$, $P= 0.007$), since the p-value obtained was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected leading to a conclusion that financial training significantly influences performance of fish projects. The current findings are supported by Turyahebwa and Ssekajugo (2013) who investigated financial training and project performance in Uganda and found that financial training positively influenced business performance. However, the findings contrast with those of Bhattacharjee (2014) who assessed financial training in India and found that advanced knowledge pertaining to investment decisions, existence of cost control, and budgeting was low. Their study however noted that enhanced financial training enhances organizational performance.

V. Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings

The researcher summarized the research findings in the order of the study objectives. The aim of summarizing was to enable the researcher to come up with key findings from which conclusions are drawn.

5.1.1 Influence of Budgeting on Performance of Fish Farming Projects

The study established that farmers usually do budget estimates before engaging themselves in fish farming projects investments (Mean = 4.18). The study also established that farmers analyze all the variable costs such as labor cost, feeds, fingerlings and include it in their fish project's budget for a given production period (Mean = 4.18). Similarly, it was found that farmers understood fixed costs such as rent and member subscriptions associated with the fish farming projects and include them in their production period budget (Mean = 4.27). Furthermore, it was found that farmers usually made production projections and hence include sales projections of their harvest in the budget for each production period (Mean = 4.20). Finally, it was established that farmers incur additional costs during the production period outside what is budgeted for (Mean = 4.24). From correlation analysis, it was established that budgeting ($r = 0.135$) had a weak positive correlation with performance of fish projects. From the regression analysis, the study established that a unit increase in budgeting would cause an increase of performance of fish projects by a factor of 0.168.

5.1.2 Influence of Standard Costing on Performance of Fish Farming Projects

The study established that that farmers usually make production cost estimates in relation to the previous production period (Mean = 4.22). Further, the study found that farmers calculate the actual production cost at the end of the production period and make comparison with the estimates made during the start of the production cycle (Mean = 4.08). Similarly, it was established that farmers calculate the cost variance to determine if there is any loss incurred during the production period (Mean =3.67). The study also found that farmers determine the harvest volume at end of production

cycle to establish any variance with the amount stocked at the start of the production cycle (Mean = 4.00). Finally, the study established that the total cost of production in fisheries projects largely determines the pricing of fish during marketing (Mean = 3.57). Further, it was established that standard costing ($r = 0.644^{**}$) had a strong positive correlation with performance of fish projects. The study further established a unit increase in standard costing would cause an increase of performance of fish projects by a factor of 0.346.

5.1.3 Influence of Financial Training on Performance of Fish Farming Projects

The study established that farmers analyze their capital position before engaging in fish farming projects (Mean = 3.88). Similarly, farmers do profit analysis of fish farming before undertaking the projects (Mean = 3.90). It was also established that farmers save part of their profit from fish farming which they use in the following production cycle or other farm investments (Mean = 4.24). The study also found that farmers keep regular track records for all activities during the production period. (Mean = 3.94). Finally, the study established that farmers normally develop market plans with their customers to minimize post-harvest spoilage by making arrangements with buyer or by contract engagements (Mean = 3.63). Further, from the correlation analysis it was established that financial training ($r = 0.637^{**}$) had a strong and positive correlation with performance of fish projects. Similarly, from the regression analysis, a unit increase in financial training would cause an increase of performance of fish projects by a factor of 0.361.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher has drawn several conclusions which are presented in this section following the order of the objectives of the study.

The researcher was able to establish the concrete evidence that both standard costing and financial training had strong correlation with the fish farming projects hence had significant influence on the dependent variable. The study also established that budget had no significant influence in fisheries projects funded by the Kiambu county government.

It was also concluded that due to the financial knowledge farmers have gained from the fisheries officers, they are able to make production predictions and forecasting and therefore was easy to make their sales projections. It was noted that despite the fact that farmers are able to make projections and including all costs in the budget, they have frequently incurred additional costs during the production period. This issue need to be addressed by both the farmers and fisheries experts so that they can minimize on cost of production hence will maximize their income since the prices of fish in the market is largely determined by the production cost. Standard costing should therefore be used as a yardstick to measure variances in the production cost.

Financial training was concluded to be a significant predictor of fish project performance. It is therefore important that financial education be included in all trainings which are done to the farmers. This would help the farmers to transfer knowledge in their practical farm engagements. With the knowledge, farmers will reduce wastage in production and maximize on production.

Recommendations

After drawing inferences in line with the study objectives, the researcher has proposed the following recommendations. The recommendations are based on the inferences drawn from the regression analysis and the conclusions drawn.

The study recommends that since budgeting had insignificant influence on performance of fish farming projects, program managers should devise simplified mechanism that will ensure farmers embrace budgeting not only as future cost estimates but as a key ingredient in the project planning process. The study also recommends engagement of all the stakeholders in developing the budgets so that to avoid deficiencies in their budgets where some areas are not catered for.

Furthermore, the study recommends that since standard costing strongly influences performance of fish farming projects, farmers should be encouraged to adopt current standard costing techniques that will allow them to easily project variation and thus give them room for financial flexibility.

Finally, the study recommends that County governments should address the issue of cost control practices in their training needs development for the farmers as well as the extension officers. Cost control practices should be included during project planning and implementation.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The study suggests that further research be conducted to investigate the influence of the other factors on performance of fish farming projects. Further, other scholars should attempt to investigate the independent variables used in this study across other sectors and industries in the Kenyan economy as better understanding of their influence will go a long way in enhancing project performance and thus improved economic performance nationally. Specifically, further research needs to be conducted to investigate budgeting in different settings and context in order to establish the source of deviations from findings in literature. Lastly, more research should be conducted to understand the comparative influence of these factors in different counties undertaking similar fish farming projects so as to enable generalization of the influence on performance of fish farming projects.

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